

“Such Is the Republic”: Vicissitudes in Atatürk’s Anticipation of Post- Ottoman Turkey

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Over the course of the Turkish War of Independence (1919-1923), Mustafa Kemal Atatürk—a former officer of the Ottoman Army—assumed leadership of the Turkish National Movement and became the first president of the Republic following its victory. In 1927, Atatürk recounted the war and his ascent to power in a seven-day address to the first congress of his Republican People’s Party. Immediately upon its delivery, this speech, “Nutuk,” became a state-sanctioned account of Turkey’s national history, and it has largely been treated as authoritative by sympathetic historians in the years since. Despite Nutuk’s ostensible influence on Kemalist history, however, two characteristics of the speech set it apart from subsequent instalments in the tradition. Firstly, it acknowledges that the Republic as it stood at the time was neither a product of premeditated ideological engineering nor purely a convenience of the postwar political climate. This nuance is most apparent in Atatürk’s denunciation of the office of Sultan-Caliph, which is initially muted and only later overt, and in his treatment of territorial severances, which he reimagines as necessary to bring about a desired ethnic homogeneity and thus preferable even if imposed by defeat. Secondly, Atatürk’s account of Turkey’s founding, which otherwise argues the gradual severance of the Ottoman and Turkish regimes, is complicated by his denial of the ethnic cleansing of Armenians between 1915 and 1921. Because it defends proponents of the old order and betrays a sympathy with it in doing so, Kemal’s twofold justification and obfuscation of genocide committed under the Ottomans suspends the narrative of growing Ottoman-Turkish dissonance that characterises the speech at large. These two facets of Nutuk illustrate how the document is more conservative in its claims about Turkey’s political and ideological foundation than the Kemalist histories that draw upon it.

From the 15th to the 20th of October 1927, Mustafa Kemal Atatürk delivered a 36-hour speech at the second congress of his Republican People’s Party (*Cumhuriyet Halk Partisi*). In doing so, he christened an official history of the Turkish Republic that inaugurated a national myth, even if it has since lost its uncontested hegemony in some circles. Narrating the War of Independence (*Kurtuluş/İstiklal Savaşı*) and its aftermath, *Nutuk* – a title under which print editions of the transcript are generally sold that translates literally to “[The] Speech,” – insists upon a territorial and ideological rupture between the Ottoman Caliphate and Turkish Republic. Atatürk’s account of Turkey’s naissance unfolds in step with an incremental shift in his sympathies between his arrival at Samsun in May 1919 and the first assembly of the Grand National Congress (*Büyük Millet Meclisi*) in April 1920 (Philliou, 2021). The process of disillusionment and estrangement he recounts underpins a distinction between Ottoman blunders and calculated sacrifices on the part of the Republic that characterises orthodox Turkish historiography (Turanoğlu, 2017).

In detailing how he gradually forsook the Ottoman cause, Atatürk signals a clear narrative conclusion from the very beginning; *Nutuk* crescendos where Empire ceases to exist, and Republic comes to be. He also reimagines the territorial imprints of late Ottoman losses, which were often the product of negotiation with foreign actors, as the result of Republican agency. Two discourses in the speech (henceforth ‘text’) capture this tendency: Atatürk’s declamation of the office of Sultan-Caliph, which is only made after he recalls the Republic’s declaration, and the reimagination of territorial losses as triages that produced a desired ethnic homogeneity within Turkey’s new borders. Parsing relevant excerpts from *Nutuk* reveals simultaneously longitudinal and teleological claims of distinction from the Ottomans. Atatürk acknowledges that the impetus for the Republic’s creation was not born of a sudden, rapturous moment, while also asserting that the trajectory it followed was not incidental. *Nutuk* essentialises the ethnically homogenous Turkish nation-state and its corresponding borders, but also insists that its realisation was gradual.

In a separate vein, Atatürk's simultaneous justification and denial of the Armenian Genocide demonstrates the incoherence of *Nutuk's* proposed Ottoman-Turkish discontinuity. Instead of reducing the Armenian Genocide to one of many Ottoman errors in the 1910s, which would allow him to distance his new order from the agents of genocide, Atatürk denies it entirely and instead claims that Armenians were aggressors in a separate case of violence against Muslims. In doing so, he absolves the preceding regime of guilt, inadvertently sympathising with the apparatus responsible for the atrocities. When Atatürk displays indignation at humanitarian indictments of the Porte's actions in eastern Anatolia, he betrays an attitude incongruent with the text at large. The intimate familiarity of the Republic's establishment with a Turkist faction in the Empire's final years means Atatürk's silencing of the genocide may be read as a reaction to accusations levelled at his compatriots. Even so, however, that rationale would still entail the admission of a political lineage immediately and ineluctably traceable to the Ottomans (see Zürcher, 2003; 2011). Atatürk further undoes his previous severance when he defends the eastern campaign of the independence struggle along confessional, not ethnolinguistic lines, which violates the Republic's then-new diktats of secularism.

Taking stock of both aspects in *Nutuk* reveals its rhetorical complexity and the relative modesty of its speaker's claims. Though he argues the inviolability of Turkey's ethnic and territorial basis, Atatürk acknowledges in the speech that its political realities were ultimately subject to historical accident. In doing so, he acknowledges that the torchbearers of the Republic were not privy to its ideal from the outset but were driven towards the idea of the new state through the events of the Independence War. The text's protagonists do not proactively work towards the realisation of an unchanging, ahistorical objective, but rather react to global circumstances, the inevitable outcome of which (the demise of the Empire and formation of the Republic) is only gradually revealed to them. In brief: Atatürk continually recounts pivotal movements in which he invariably made auspicious choices motivated by strategy, not ideology. (Competent) Reaction, not proaction, characterises his narrative. This culminated in the realisation—not invention—of the Republic. As a caveat, closure of the revolution described in *Nutuk* is rendered incomplete by Atatürk's adamant denial of the Armenian Genocide, which implies the continued pertinence of an Ottoman episode to the speaker that draws him into its fray.

FROM SUPREME CALIPH TO CRAVEN SOVEREIGN: THE REINVENTION OF THE SULTAN

In October 1918, the Armistice of Mudros closed the Ottoman theatre of the First World War, only for armed conflict to erupt again the following year with a Greek occupation of the Anatolian mainland. This coincided with what Atatürk recollects as an opportunistic and unlawful Armenian invasion in the east, equivalent to that in the west. "[A]ll over the country, Christian elements were struggling to procure their secret aims, causing the state to collapse meanwhile," he recounts (Kemal, 2019). On both fronts, the military defence of Anatolia— "a fatherland in which only a few Turks took shelter"—was organised not by the Ottoman army, but by a plethora of post-war regional resistance campaigns (*cemiyetler*) soon to coalesce under the Anatolian or National Movement (*Anadolu/Millî/Milliyetçi Hareketi*) (Kemal, 2019, p. 14). Among these, the Central-Eastern Anatolian (*Şarkî Anadolu Müdafaa-i Hukuk Cemiyeti*) and that of the Black Sea coast (*Trabzon Muhafaza-i Hukuku Milliye Cemiyeti*) were particularly significant as it was within their jurisdictions that the Erzurum and Sivas Congresses were held, and primarily from their ranks that members of the unified Representative Committee responsible for issuing communiques were drawn.

With these assemblies, a syndicate of unsanctioned, interior-Anatolian militias (except the *Trakya Paşaeli*, which operated in Thrace) came to resemble something of an organised revolutionary movement, a stature underpinned by a manifesto disseminated in the *Amasya Circular* of June 1919. This document asserted, among other things, that "1. The integrity of the country and the nation are at great risk," "2. The government in Istanbul is unable to fulfil its responsibilities," and "3. The independence of the nation will be salvaged by its determination" (Kemal, 2019, p. 29). In October of that year, the National Movement, now a quasi-state, enjoyed official recognition by the Istanbulite counterpart it had previously labelled illegitimate with the *Amasya Pact* (*Amasya Görüşmesi*). The *Görüşme* was a memorandum of understanding between the National Movement and Ottomans that called for immediate elections to fill the lower house of parliament (*Meclis-i Mebusân*). While the content of the pact is beyond the scope of this paper, the fact that it implied the equivalence of parallel governments in Istanbul and Sivas through their mutual status as signatories is noteworthy.

Whatever limited cooperation the protocol facilitated did not last, however, because the failure of the Istanbul Government to expel a Franco-British occupation of the city in early 1920 constituted, according

to *Nutuk*, a violation of the National Oath (*Misak-ı Millî*). Pre-empted in 1919 but only explicitly outlined in the final meeting of the *Meclis-i Mebusân* in January 1920, the *Misak* asserted the sacrosanctity of the empire's borders on the eve of the war, which exceeded the extent of Turkey's current borders in the Caucasus, Mesopotamia, and the Levant (Batuman, 2010). The Treaty of Sevrés, signed in August between grand vizier Damat Ferit Paşah and representatives from the wartime Entente, was seen as a further and this time irredeemably egregious breach of the Oath. The terms agreed upon at Sevrés provisioned an independent Armenia and autonomous Kurdish region within the Ottoman rump state, and validated Greek occupation of the Mediterranean Coast.

In response to the earlier transgression, the first Grand National Assembly was held in Ankara in April 1920, its stated mission being to “[rescue] the supreme Caliphate, the office of the Sultanate, and the country from foreign powers” (Neziroğlu, 2015). Thereafter, on the eve of Sevrés, the nationalists undertook a military campaign against not only non-Turkish nationalist movements in Anatolia and incursions by former Entente powers (namely France in Cilicia), but the government in Istanbul as well. This second leg of the Independence War culminated in the victory of the National Movement and the consequent declaration of the Republic. The inception of the Republic of Turkey (*Türkiye Cumhuriyeti*) is generally marked by the Treaty of Lausanne in 1923, which saw the Sultanate abolished and the new state garner official recognition by colonial powers in Europe. In the interim, the National Movement signed the Treaty of Moscow with the Soviet Union, the latter officially recognising the “Government of the Grand National Assembly of Turkey” as, rather than a provisional contingency measure, the permanent political apparatus of a new, legitimate state. The Caliphate, a final vestige of the Ottoman monarchy after 1922, was done away with in 1924.

All this is to say that *de facto* legitimacy and the scope of competing claims to governance were incrementally rebalanced in the early 1920s. As the National Movement gained momentum, it was increasingly reckoned as a suzerain government both locally and internationally, and increasingly donned the corresponding stature in its affairs. Concurrent with sovereignty's eastward shift, there was an adjustment of the National Movement's objective: where it had initially been conceived as an emergency measure intended to secure the survival of the Sultanate and Empire, it increasingly became the revolutionary foundation for a new, distinctly post-Ottoman political project. Whatever concerns accompanied the abolition of the monarchy in the 1920s were undoubtedly a far cry from those that called for “rescuing the supreme Caliphate [and] the office of the Sultanate,” in 1919.

This polar shift is echoed in *Nutuk*. Though the speech opens with a reproach of Sultan Vahdettin and Damat Ferit Paşa, their respective offices do not become the target of its censure until later. The initial castigation is entirely personal:

Vahdettin, who occupied the throne and the caliphate, was degenerate, looking to guarantee his own life and the throne only. His cabinet, headed by Damat Ferit Paşah, was impotent, inglorious, and cowardly, obedient to the will of this Sultan only... (Kemal, 2019, p. 12).

It is only over the course of several episodes during which Atatürk professes his and the National Movement's naïveté that the target of his polemics shifts from personages towards the relevant institutions in which they were implicated. In the beginning, condemnation almost immediately gives way to a muted apology for the Sultan, mimicking a bygone optimism for integration of the office within a reinvigorated state. In a note attached to his opening remarks at the 1920 sitting of the Grand National Congress, Atatürk optimistically predicted that “as soon as the Sultan-Caliph is delivered from all pressure and coercion he will take his place within the frame of legislative principles which will be determined by the Assembly” (Kemal, 2019, p. 333).

There are also times when this apology veers into a confession of Machiavellian neglect of Vahdettin's treason in the interests of preserving the integrity of the country. This is best demonstrated by Atatürk's recollection of an incident immediately prior to the Sivas Congress in which Ali Galip Bey, then governor of Elazığ (formerly a predominantly Armenian vilayet mostly repopulated at this time by Kurds), facilitated a minor insurrection by members of the Bedirxanî tribe (Sipahi, 2018; Low, 2022). Speaking on his response to the issue, Atatürk recounts that:

Ali Galip's enterprise was a joint attempt by the Sultan, Ferit Paşah's Cabinet, and [the British]. The attitude to adopt towards such treachery is clear. But, it would have been wise to avoid moving openly in counter attacks and to avoid [diluting] our attention across several targets, we focused it on one point. Therefore, we chose Ferit Paşa's Cabinet as our only target and pretended that we didn't know that the Sultan was also involved. Our *theory* [my emphasis] was that the Cabinet was deceiving the Sultan by not telling him what was really going on... We pretended as if we were convinced that the Sultan would punish the ones who deceived him as soon as he was made clearly aware of the facts... (Kemal, 2019, p. 122).

The implicit aim here is to preserve a hierarchical *status quo*. Instead of either re-writing this moment as one of Republican breakage from the Sultanate or admitting that the Republicans were unable or unwilling to do away with the Sultan at this time, the question of denouncing the throne is bypassed entirely, and the nationalists' course of action reimagined as the most strategic reaction to an isolated treason on the part of its current occupant. In a consequent telegram to the Sultan, the Representative Committee wrote that:

The government has attempted to shed the blood of Muslims by planning to attack the Congress with armed men. It has also been proven by certain documents that they received money to dismember our territory by inciting Kurdistan in revolt (Kemal, 2019, p. 112).

The significance of this communique lies in the distinction between the Sultan, a recipient included in the "our" of "our territory," and the Istanbul Government, to which the telegram refers in the third person. The target of the committee's admonition in this message is not the monarch himself but his cadre instead.

The incident detailed in the above excerpt unfolded immediately before communication was cut between Anatolia and Istanbul by order of Kemal, a moment often taken to mark the absolute severance of the National Movement from Istanbul and the start of a new phase of the conflict (Zürcher, 1986). However, the feeble incompetence of a particular Sultan has yet to translate into the malignant decadence of the entire office in Atatürk's account. Such an assertion would have to wait until a monologue concerning the first session of the Lausanne conference (in late 1922). In a passage relevant to that meeting, Atatürk remarks that "questions brought forward on the agenda did not exclusively concern the new regime, which was only three or four years old," retroactively reclassifying the entire duration covered by the text as part of the Republican period (Kemal, 2019, p. 565). With this, the liminal period between the coalescence of a viable alternative command structure and the deposition of that in Istanbul is reimagined as the first years of the former's sovereignty.

A categorical denunciation of the Caliphate is first unambiguously articulated in Atatürk's correspondence with an editor of the (originally Young Turk-affiliated) periodical *Tanin* in November 1923. Here, he writes that:

great sagacity is by no means required to understand that a form of government demanding an unconditional adherence to the Caliphate is irreconcilable with the Republic [...] The enlightened republican sons of Turkey [...] will easily understand that it was impossible to maintain a form of government which, after having proclaimed itself a republic, would have undertaken the obligation of preserving, with the Caliph at its head, a rotten dynasty (Kemal, 2019, p. 659).

In this final instance, he admits the irreconcilability of the monarchy with the Republic, but only after recounting several years in which he did not consider his and the nationalists' work to be incompatible with the preservation of the Ottoman dynasty in some capacity. This culmination is not a revelatory moment at which the Sultanate is suddenly disavowed, but an exercise in the reconciliation of an ideologically sanctioned historical conclusion with the winding road that occasioned it. Here, Atatürk makes clear that the Republic, at least beginning in 1923, became incompatible with the continued presence of a monarchy, and with this, reimagines his previous efforts to preserve the dynasty as strategic compromises rather than ends in themselves. His condemnation of Vahdettin and Damat Ferit Paşah is,

at this point, extended to their respective institutions. The narrative is reworked even within the confines of the text to retroactively circumscribe the range of possible histories.

FROM IMPERIAL BLUNDER TO REPUBLICAN SACRIFICE: THE TREATMENT OF TERRITORIAL LOSSES

Republican Turkey's territorial bounds—outlined at Moscow in 1921 and Lausanne in 1923 and then marginally expanded in 1939 with the addition of Hatay—fall far short of those described by the *Misak-ı Milli*, the violation of which constituted a turning point in Atatürk's indictment of the Sultanate. This detail is scarcely confronted in the speech, the territorial genesis of modern Turkey appearing largely seamless. Any trauma therein is relocated to prior Ottoman defeats or the threat of future loss. The mortal capitulations decided at Sévres, for instance, are categorised as known and unacceptable worst-case outcomes of a possible defeat for the young nation-state, not the actual consequences of one that occurred and were then only partially undone. That the borders of Sévres are not taken for granted is evinced by Atatürk describing the treaty as conducive to the “dismemberment of Turkey [that] thank God has not been realised” (Kemal, 2019, p. 101).

This characterisation of the treaty is emblematic of another choice within *Nutuk*: the use of the phrase “our country” with neither regard nor explanation for the changing referent of that term. The name “Turkey” appears inconsistently—it is used, at different points throughout the text, to refer to the Ottoman rump state in Anatolia, the full extent of the *Misak-ı Milli*, and Turkey as of 1923. This, of course, is significant unto itself, the ambiguity of the area meant by “our country” or “Turkey” constituting part of a strategy to obscure failure that seizes upon the shifting demands made by Republicans during the Independence War. With regards to the thesis of this essay, the active obfuscation of where the Empire ends, and Republic begins, plays into the characterisation of Turkey's coalescence as organic.

Where Atatürk does register concessions, it is to highlight their role in bolstering Turkey's ethnic homogeneity, which for him constitutes the fundamental basis for a state's continued survival: “to unite different nations under one common name, to give these different elements equal rights, subject them to the same conditions, and thus to found a mighty state is a brilliant and attractive political ideal, but it is a misleading one,” he writes (Kemal, 2019, p. 331). For Atatürk, such multinationalism characterised the Ottoman regime:

In a state which extends from the East to the West and which unites in its embrace contrary elements with opposite characteristics, goals, and cultures, it is natural that the internal organisation should be defective and weak in its foundations ... For this reason, the policy of the Ottoman State could not be national and was deficient in clarity and continuity (Kemal, 2019, p. 331).

Therefore, when he recalls that parts of western Georgia including Batumi—awarded to Turkey in the 1920 Treaty of Gümrü (Alexandropol) signed between Turkey and Armenia—were ceded to the USSR in the Treaty of Moscow the following year, he makes sure to draw attention to the inclusion of Artvin and Trabzon within Turkey's final iteration, which “took place amidst the enthusiasm of the inhabitants, who had impatiently awaited their union with Turkey” (Kemal, 2019, p. 377). In this instance, the admission of surrender is accompanied by the reaffirmation of the correspondence between a mostly Anatolian post-war Turkey and an ethnolinguistic body corresponding to that the state claimed to represent.

Both the ambiguity with which territorial losses are revealed and their reassessment as a means towards ethnic homogeneity contribute to building an account in which the actors in the Independence War stumble (for lack of a better word) into the realisation of new order. In response to the vivisection of the Ottoman Empire, Atatürk invents a narrative that takes care to simultaneously assert the agency of his Republicans in deciding Turkey's borders while maintaining that its final silhouette was something serendipitous. Turkey's 1927 borders, though auspicious, are not treated in *Nutuk* as the result of a premeditated campaign to secure a set territorial reach, but rather the fruits of an instinctive self-defence effort. Here, as elsewhere, the Republicans are characterised as resolutely reactive, not proactive.

Turkey's territory is an especially crucial subject of the national myth because of its intimacy with the traumas of the Ottoman collapse. In 1927, a narrative shift that reframed Anatolia as a yet-unpenetrated bastion of sovereignty—as opposed to a backwater to now lost Ottoman territories—was imperative for the engineers of the Republic's mythos (Atakuman, 2008). There were several reasons behind this. Firstly,

acknowledging Ottoman losses beyond Anatolia as their own would imply the foreignness of the Republican heroes for whom the terrain of the new Serbian, Greek, and Bulgarian nation-states were birthplaces. Because the vanguards of this emerging nation-state's territorial integrity could not be refugees of conceded territory—his would violate the assertion, integral in the new rhetoric of the Turkish state, of total isomorphism between the Turkish nation and the Republic's territorial extent—heir political legitimacy was contingent upon the confession of their Anatolian-ness. More importantly, reasserting an attachment to the Balkans would also symbolically implicate the country's founders in the perceived blunders of the Ottoman autumn, numbering them among the incompetent new order statesmen and generals that failed to see the Empire through the 1910s. Lastly, to take up the Ottomans' symbolic boundaries would have been to sanction an irredentism that, in the 1920s, risked compromising both the diplomatic and political stature of the new state. Turkey could not afford, literally or figuratively, to pursue a campaign of expansion in the Balkans nor foster sentiment that would justify one. At the moment of the nation-state's creation, it would have been highly unstrategic to explicitly admit its incompleteness. Instead, an ambiguity was maintained that could be exploited to conjure the requisite basis for expansionism later, as happened in Hatay in the following decade.

A POLICY OF MURDER AND EXTERMINATION: SUSPENSION OF THE OTTOMAN-TURKISH DIVORCE

The late nineteenth century was marked by a cascade of genocides inaugurated by the Circassian and culminating in “Armenian massacres which, by the way, did not exist,” according to Atatürk (Kemal, 2019, p. 276). Beginning with the reign of Sultan Abdulhamit II in the 1870s, pogroms of Armenians in the east unfolded under the ascendancy of his eponymous Light Cavalry: contingents of mostly Kurdish mounted irregulars reporting directly to the Padişah (Klein, 2011). Despite a series of massacres under the leadership of one Zeki (later Kılıçoğlu) Paşah, the dispossession and wholesale extermination of Armenians would not begin until the Second Constitutional Period (Klein, 2011). Under the Committee of Union and Progress (*İttihad ve Terakki Cemiyeti*, ‘CUP’) that seized power upon the abdication of Sultan Abdulhamit, the corps were renamed to the ‘Tribal’ Light Cavalry (*Aşiret Hafif Süvari Alayları*) (Klein, 2011). This iteration of the corps, along with the shadowy ‘Special Organization’ (*Teşkilât-ı Mahsusa*) headed by several prominent members of the CUP, carried out the forced relocation and systematic genocide of Armenian communities during the First World War (Üngör, 2012).

That the eradication of Armenians peaked under the Ottomans does not mean that it and the sentiment underlying it were absent in the ensuing independence struggle. Despite the considerable death toll incurred by those sent on the death march to Urfa and Deir ez-Zor, many survived the journey and persisted in squalid conditions upon their arrival. A sizeable contingent of these survivors was later encouraged by European occupation forces to relocate to Cilicia and became a persistent thorn in the side of the National Movement as it sought to wrestle control of the area from the French (Kévorkian, 2021). Moreover, many attempted throughout 1919 and 1920 to reclaim their ancestral homes in Anatolia and the Caucasus where, by this point, Muslim refugees (*Mucahirliler*) from the Balkans had already been resettled *en masse* (Kévorkian, 2021). Naturally, violence ensued, culminating in the eastern campaign of the Independence War led by Kazım Karabekir against the short-lived Republic of Armenia (Kévorkian, 2021). Defeat of the Armenian Republic is often taken to constitute the “first victory” of the Turkish, much of the territory reclaimed from Armenia codified in the 1921 Treaty of Moscow.

So far, I have made the case that *Nutuk* does articulate the Ottoman-Turkish rupture, albeit not as something instantaneous. There is no disidentification between Turkey and the Ottoman Empire, however, in passages where Atatürk works to naturalise an ethnic homogeneity produced only through ethnic cleansing and justify atrocities committed under the old regime. By making it so that “the victims of yesterday emerge on the stage of history as the perpetrators of tomorrow,” in the words of David Leupold, Atatürk inadvertently fails to disentangle the new nation from its Ottoman past (Leupold, 2020, p. 15). Evidence for this appears even in the first instance in which he describes the purpose of the Association for the Defence of Law in Anatolia and Rumelia (later subsumed into the National Movement), which he says was created “to maintain the rights of the Turks in the eastern provinces as well as to expose to the civil world with convincing documents that the Turkish people were absolutely not involved in maltreatment during the deportation [of Armenians] and that Armenian properties were preserved until the Russian invasion, and on the other hand Muslim people were exposed to very cruel acts” (Leupold, 2020; Kemal, 2019, p. 7).

There is a frantic series of claims made in this excerpt that stresses both the categorical innocence (and even victimhood) of Turks and the ignobility of Armenians—that the speaker feels either is necessary suggests an identification with a regime against which charges of genocide were levelled, an establishment that the rest of the speech would suggest he came to disavow between 1919 and 1920. He, moreover, neglects to disentangle the category of ‘Turk’ from Muslim Ottoman more broadly. Where, much later in the speech, he remarks that “our nation had never taken up an aggressive stance against any foreigners without good reason,” Atatürk again conflates the “our nation” instituted in 1920 with that of 1915 (Kemal, 2019, p. 277). He also takes care to account for the possibility that Turks were more than just passive victims with the caveat “without good reason.” The sentiment is, paradoxically, that claims of violence against Armenians were categorically false, but that the alleged violence was also a response to some prior conflict. This contention is articulated more substantially in the following passage:

The assertions regarding the Armenian massacres were undoubtedly not in accordance with fact. For, the Armenians in the south, armed by foreign troops and encouraged by the protection they enjoyed, attacked the Muslims in their districts. / Animated with the spirit of revenge, they pursued a relentless policy of murder and extermination everywhere [...] The Armenians were instigators of the atrocities, which were unique in history (Kemal, 2019, p. 176).

Here, Armenians are simultaneously “animated with the spirit of revenge” but also “instigators of atrocities.” Atatürk seemingly overlooks the mutual exclusivity of these claims. The incoherency of this defence is further reinforced when the speaker attempts to deny the very presence of Armenians who might serve as the target of violence:

“The question of ceding a part of the territory of the Eastern Provinces to Armenia is mentioned. However, it is not only practically impossible today to cede even an inch of this territory, in which a majority of inhabitants are Turks and Kurds, to the Armenians, but, due to the severity and horridness of the thirst for revenge that prevails among these elements, it would also be dangerous to intensely settle even the Ottoman Armenians in these provinces if they returned. In this respect, the greatest accommodation that could be granted to the innocent Ottoman Armenians would be nothing but letting them return to their country on equitable and equal terms” (Kemal, 2019, p. 90).

Atatürk also stresses, in explaining why he could not accept a mandate for Armenia under the stewardship of the League of Nations or the United States, that:

[Even] before the war, the inhabitants of these districts consisted of a predominantly Turkish majority, a small population of Kurds, who are called “Zaza,” and an insignificant number of Armenians. And today, there are almost no Armenians—that isn’t even worth mentioning (Kemal, 2019, p. 90).

Coupled with the previous polemics, the claim that there were no major Armenian communities in the eastern provinces is part of a historical reconstruction integral to Turkish nation-building. In denying a significant pre-war Armenian presence, Atatürk not only downplays the violence committed by the ancient regime but also lays the groundwork to deny competing claims to indigeneity in the area. He repurposes his denial of Ottoman persecution of Armenians to make essential Turkish settlement in the area. However, in making use of this tactic, he also reverses the difference from the Ottomans upon which he otherwise tactfully insists.

In the interest of brevity, I have omitted a discussion of how *Nutuk* approaches the Kurdish question in the aftermath of the Sheikh Said Rebellion of 1925, however the fact that Atatürk persists in acknowledging a (non-Turkish) Zaza presence in the area of Dersim is atypical of Turkish rhetoric at the time, and presents a second complication in this aspect of the text (Deniz, 2020). With regard to the Kurdish question, the speaker indulges, in separate instances both tacitly and overtly, the notion of a body politic characterised by a shared confessional identity (Islam), not a language or national cause. In doing so, he draws upon the Islamic nationalism of the later CUP period in which Kurds, Turks, and others were lumped together as Muslim Ottoman citizens in opposition to “Christian elements.” This is highly ironic given Turkey’s increasingly militant secularisation at the time of the speech and the increasing association of Islamism with Kurdish secessionism (Klein, 2011; Yavuz, 2001; Zeydanlioğlu, 2012).

The years immediately preceding this speech saw the Turkish state mandate a civic, linguistic, geographical, and secular basis for national identity. This inevitably generated contradictions with regard to groups like Kurds that, despite falling within the geographical extent of the new Turkey and despite their participation in the National Movement during the Independence War, remained beyond the reach of secularising and linguistically homogenising policies in the 1920s. The suspension of the independence struggle's national basis in favour of a confessional one constitutes a strategy to include non-Turkic Muslim minorities within its scope, thus naturalising their presence within the borders of modern Turkey. However, this strategy gives rise to a contradiction in Atatürk's narrative insofar as it frames Turkey's citizenry as confessionally defined and indistinguishable from that of the Ottoman Empire on the eve of its collapse. Examining of how *Nutuk* approaches the Armenian problem, therefore, lays bare the identitarian hazards of *Nutuk's* national myth: in the process of constructing an official history that embraces the Republic's fortuitous emergence as something engendered, albeit inevitably, by historical accident, Atatürk fails to fully disentangle its demography from that of the Empire.

KEMAL VERSUS KEMALISTS: POINTS OF DIVERGENCE BETWEEN NUTUK AND LATER HISTORIES

The caveats I have attempted to identify in the foregoing force a re-evaluation of the relationship between *Nutuk* and the Kemalist tradition in Turkish history. Proponents of this approach, most of whom ostensibly embrace the authority of *Nutuk*, point to events like the debut of the Grand National Assembly or the cessation of communication with Istanbul in 1919 as moments of total rupture wrought by the heroic efforts of a newly self-conscious national community. They also echo *Nutuk's* identification of Armenian demands for independence within Anatolia as a project orchestrated by opportunistic imperial powers, this paranoia often falling under the umbrella of 'Sèvres Syndrome' in reference to the 1920 peace treaty vilified by Atatürk (Gökçek, 2008). It is a family of theses for which specimens have also been produced by non-Turkish authors. Consider the following passage from Andrew Mango's non-academic (and largely hagiographic) *Atatürk*:

Atatürk earned his place in history by directing the successful resistance of the Muslim inhabitants of Anatolia against the occupation and attempted partition of their country ... But from the moment he was chosen chairman of the Erzurum congress in 1919 to the time when the victory of the Turkish resistance received international recognition at Lausanne in 1923, he was in charge of the forces of Turkish nationalism (Mango, 1999, p. 532).

In bracketing the incident of militant Turkish nationalism against the Porte, Mango indulges a tendency endemic to histories of this transformational period that fails to acknowledge the gradient nature of the Ottoman-Turkish split. Revolution was only one component of this change, and most certainly not one foreseen before it was set in motion. There was an aspect of accident in how the National Movement came to be and unfolded thereafter, and it is one acknowledged by the speaker in *Nutuk* but often neglected by historians of the topic.

A more revealing example of how orthodox Kemalist history neglects the nuances of *Nutuk* can be found in Sina Akşin's essay, "The Nature of the Kemalist Revolution." Akşin taught in Turkey and served as the deputy chairman of the Atatürkist Thought Association—his work in this capacity is representative of the Kemalist tradition. In this essay, he makes the claim that:

"From time to time one comes across certain observers who seem to assume that the Kemalist Revolution was a sort of personal program of Atatürk, imposed on an unwilling nation by a victorious leader who had saved it from disaster. If this were the case, the Revolution would not have survived him for long. [...] Thus, we have to come to the conclusion that the Revolution was an objective necessity, not the whim of a dictator. Let us now see what that necessity was. / Thanks to the War of Independence, [...] disaster was averted, and the Treaty of Lausanne replaced that of Sèvres. But it became clear that to make the Treaty of Lausanne permanent, the backward social, political, cultural conditions of Turkish society had to undergo radical revolutionary change. That is precisely what the Kemalist Revolution set out to do. It is also the reason why the Revolution has stood fast for so long. If the Revolution had not been launched, it was very likely that the Treaty of Sèvres, or something similar would have reappeared on the first occasion" (Akşin, 2008, pp. 2016-17).

In doing so, Akşin, like Mango, approaches the National Movement's Independence War ahistorically. Akşin takes it and its consequences to be inevitabilities and stresses an agency on the part of Atatürk and his cadre that is not substantiated by his own account in *Nutuk*. He speaks about "precisely what the Kemalist Revolution set out to do," when Atatürk himself in *Nutuk* recognises that there was no such clarity at the time of the fact.

Atatürk surmised that "under Ottoman rule, various political doctrines were held. For my part, I had arrived at the conviction that none of these doctrines could be accepted by the political organisation of the new Turkey" (Kemal, 2019, p. 329). This verbiage of "[having] arrived" encapsulates an attitude often overlooked in histories that seek to echo Nutuk's official line. In reifying aspirations of nationalist republicanism as a miraculous conception preceding the independence struggle, a significant lot of writers in the Kemalist tradition entertain an anachronism disingenuous to their *mythistorical* document. *Nutuk* is, in a sense, more modest than the historical canon that takes it as a starting point.

CONCLUSION

My point of departure for this study was the assumption that neither the Republic nor its territorial bounds were pre-empted at the outset of the Independence War. As related in *Nutuk*, the aim of the nationalist insurgency was initially the preservation of the Ottoman dynasty and the assurance of the Empire's 1914 borders. The referent of the phrase "our country" or "our nation" over the first several days of the speech is the jurisdiction of the Sublime Porte on the eve of the First World War, which contained "Christian elements" and areas ultimately excluded from the new Turkey. As the speech progresses, there is a piecemeal disavowal of the Sultanate and a reduction in the territory denoted by phrases like "our country." Both changes were, according to Atatürk, desirable and inevitable, but neither as planned nor deliberately sought out in the first place. In short: *Nutuk* approaches the independence struggle as prior and necessary to the conception (in the broadest sense) of modern Turkey. The articulation of a non-Ottoman political project proceeds in step with historical contingencies, and its proponents are more aptly characterised by reaction than proaction.

Complicating that process of differentiation is the issue of the Armenian Genocide, the height of which took place before the Independence War, but the troubled memories of which nonetheless persisted beyond 1923 to harass *Nutuk's* narrator. Atatürk's incessant denial of ethnic cleansing and complementary claim that Armenians and other "malicious peoples" were, in fact, perpetrators of their own campaigns of genocide directed towards Muslims establishes a continuity between the speech of 1927 and events of the 1910s. This prevents the completion of the Ottoman-Turkish severance he describes. That the denial of Armenian indigeneity and genocide is conveyed in a rebuttal of accusations against the Ottoman regime, and specifically the Committee of Union and Progress, indicates an identification with the parties responsible that is otherwise denied in the speech. It is interesting that Atatürk elsewhere persists in labelling the CUP as treacherous. Where he works to silence the traumas of genocide, Atatürk answers for the Ottomans in a case where, assuming the coherency and comprehensiveness of the break detailed in *Nutuk*, there would be no impetus to do so.

In speaking of a "post-Ottoman Turkey," I stress that *Nutuk* is an eschatology of the Sultanate. Beyond a manifesto of the Turkish Republic and vindication of its speaker's actions during the Independence War, it traces the gradual emergence of the ideological and territorial Turkey out of the Empire. Atatürk refers to Turkey not as an entirely self-contained project, the *sui generis* manifestation of an unprecedented and previously inert body politic animated only by a Promethean nationalism, but as, in his words, the "successor" of the Ottoman Empire. In doing so, he admits that it was not born of an instant of national enlightenment and self-awareness but rather a mere reordering of political life. This reads as highly idiosyncratic when compared with later state-sympathetic histories of modern Turkey's inception that neglect the modesty of Atatürk's claims. In a sentence: *Nutuk* sketches the Republic as a product of accident, however complete and desirable its existence and severance from the imperial regime.

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